

A Delphi survey to identify Informed Health Choices Key Concepts relevant for decision making related to traditional, complementary and integrative medicine: Protocol

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Background

Traditional, complementary, alternative and integrative medicine (TCIM) is widely used worldwide, either alongside or instead of biomedical care, and forms an important part of self-care for maintaining health and wellbeing. It can be difficult to make choices about TCIM, like all healthcare decisions, due to an abundance of claims about what people should do to protect, maintain or improve their physical, mental or social health and well-being. Making choices about TCIM, like all healthcare decisions, depends on health literacy – particularly the ability to evaluate the credibility of claims and to make decisions based on trustworthy evidence.

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines health literacy as: "The cognitive and social skills which determine the motivation and ability of individuals to gain access to, understand and use information in ways that promote and maintain good health." (WHO 1998). Critical health literacy is defined as "the ability to obtain, understand and critically appraise different sources of information, and the ability to engage in shared decision making." (Oxman 2020).

In response to the overwhelming amount of claims we encounter daily from friends, family or social media, we developed the Informed Health Choices (IHC) Key Concepts in 2012 as part of the IHC project that focuses on helping people to "critically appraise information about effects and to make informed health choices" (Oxman 2020; Dahlgren et al. 2022).

The current 2022 IHC Key Concepts Framework includes 49 Key Concepts, or principles for evaluating the reliability (trustworthiness) of treatment claims and the evidence used to support these, and for making informed choices. The term "treatment" in this paper refers to "any intervention or action intended to protect or improve health" (Oxman 2020).

The 49 Key Concepts are organised into three broad categories:

1. **Claims** – effects not supported by fair comparisons are not necessarily wrong, but there is an insufficient basis for believing them.
2. **Comparisons** – studies should use fair comparisons to minimise bias and random error when identifying treatment effects.
3. **Choices** – consider the problem, the relevance of available evidence, and the balance of expected benefits, harms and costs.

Over the last decade, we have developed and evaluated various learning resources to help facilitate critical thinking about health claims using the Key Concept framework. Building on the previous experience of developing IHC learning resources, this project will develop additional specific resources to facilitate informed decision-making about TCIM for the WHO online toolkit called Your Life Your Health (Muscat et al. 2023).

However, existing health literacy models may not fully capture the complexity and context-specific aspects of decisions about TCIM. While these models emphasize competencies related to obtaining, understanding, and appraising information to make decisions, they may not account for social, cultural, emotional and experiential factors that often influence decision-making processes related to TCIM. For example, TCIM choices are often influenced by cultural beliefs such as "natural means safe" or "traditional use proves effectiveness" (Agu et al., 2019; Barnes et al., 2018; Tangkiatkumjai et al., 2020), and trusting traditional knowledge handed-down from elders or traditional practitioners, along with other information sources accessed via the internet or through social networks (Tangkiatkumjai et al., 2020; Agu et al., 2019; Barnes et al., 2018; McIntyre et al., 2020).

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Cultural, spiritual, and philosophical values, diverse TCIM-specific languages and constructs, and skepticism toward modern science (Zhang et al. 2024), further complicate efforts to translate general health literacy tools into TCIM-relevant guidance. These features have prompted the development of TCIM-specific assessment tools in some contexts (Qian et al., 2023). Therefore, it remains unclear how the IHC Key Concepts are currently considered in relation to judging TCIM claims, whether certain IHC concepts are especially salient for TCIM, or whether additional or adapted concepts are required. While we acknowledge the multitude of frameworks with which one can approach decision making related to TCIM, this project was specifically initiated and funded to explore how IHC Key Concepts can be used to support decision making about TCIM.

Before initiating this Delphi study, and to address some of the research questions in the larger project, we conducted a rapid scoping review of primary studies to identify the concepts and beliefs related to assessing claims about TCIM approaches that are reported by people making choices about TCIM. We then mapped these concepts onto the IHC Key Concepts. The results of this scoping review are not publicly available yet, but we present below some of the preliminary results that will inform the Delphi.

Preliminary findings indicate that the majority of results from the included studies mapped to the “Claims” and “Choices” categories. Some of the most common Key Concepts were:

- 1.1a Do not assume that treatments are safe.
- 1.2a Do not assume that a plausible explanation of how or why a treatment might work is a sufficient basis for a claim about treatment effects.
- 1.2b Do not assume that association is the same as causation.
- 1.3c Do not assume that a treatment is helpful or safe based on how widely used it is or has been.
- 1.4a Do not assume that personal experiences alone are sufficient.
- 1.4b Do not assume that your beliefs are correct.
- 1.4c Do not assume that opinions alone are sufficient.
- 1.4e Do not assume that there are no competing interests.
- 3.2a Weigh the benefits and savings against the harms and costs of acting or not.
- 3.2b Consider the baseline risk or severity of the symptoms when estimating the size of expected effects.
- 3.2c Consider how important each advantage and disadvantage is when weighing the pros and cons and making choices.

While the scoping review provides a snapshot of the most frequently mentioned IHC Key Concepts in studies of people making decisions about using TCIM, the review is limited in comprehensiveness; due to pragmatic constraints the search strategy was very specific, and we only included studies reported in English. Given the global, culturally diverse and value-laden contexts in which TCIM is used, a structured consensus process is needed to prioritize which concepts are most important for the general public when assessing TCIM claims and to determine where adaptations or new concepts are warranted.

The Delphi technique is well suited to this task because it systematically combines the knowledge and perspectives of diverse experts and stakeholders while preserving anonymity, reducing dominance bias and enabling convergence toward consensus (Hohmann et al. 2018). Using the scoping review as an empirical foundation, an international eDelphi will provide a transparent mechanism to refine and prioritise IHC Key Concepts for TCIM, and identify any TCIM-specific adaptations or further concepts that should be added. Finally, broad consensus can help to ensure that any TCIM health literacy materials developed as part of the larger project are globally relevant, culturally sensitive, and supportive of safe, informed decision-making about TCIM.

Objective

The objective of this study is to develop a list of the most relevant IHC Key Concepts for assessing claims related to, and making decisions about traditional, complementary and integrative medicine.

Specifically, we will aim to answer the following research questions:

1. Are there any concepts specific to TCIM not currently covered by existing IHC Key Concepts?
2. Which IHC Key Concepts (including those identified in question 1) are most relevant for making informed decisions related to TCIM?

Methods

Figure 1. Overview of Delphi process

Study design

We will conduct an online Delphi consensus survey (eDelphi) to collect and analyze feedback from a group of experts and interest holders to achieve consensus on the relevant IHC key concepts for TCIM.

The Delphi technique is commonly used to gather opinions and feedback from a group of relevant experts, and to achieve consensus on a product (Turoff & Linstone 2002). We will follow guidance set forth by Conducting and Reporting Delphi Studies (Jünger et al. 2017). This Delphi process will have three parts (see Figure 1).

1. Introductory seminar: In this stage we will introduce the project to panel members.

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2. eDelphi survey: In this stage we will conduct three rounds of the eDelphi process to exclude irrelevant criteria, and compile and prioritize relevant criteria. We will use the eDelphi method to reach consensus on which key concepts are most relevant when assessing health claims about TCIM. Key concepts will include the 49 IHC Key Concepts as well as any key concepts identified through the scoping review (see above) or by panelists during Round 1 (see below) (Wieland et al. 2025). The major advantage of a Delphi consensus-reaching method is that respondents remain anonymous, thereby encouraging honest answers unlikely to be biased from peer pressure or majority opinions (France et al. 2015). The result of the Delphi will be a list of IHC Key Concepts used to develop health literacy messages (WP2).

In the first round we will divide the panelists in two groups. One group will be asked to give feedback regarding relevance of half of the IHC Key Concepts (24-25 concepts) and the second group will be asked for feedback on the other half of the Key Concepts (24-25 concepts). The complete set of IHC Key Concepts will be divided equally (half of Key Concepts for each category of concepts to each group) between the two groups (see Appendix 2 for an overview of the concepts included in each survey). This is to decrease the length of the survey and increase the likelihood of completion. All panelists will also be provided with the full list of IHC Key Concepts (e.g., a list of the key concepts they are not asked to score will be provided at the end of the eDelphi form). The Key Concepts for which panel members have achieved consensus in Round one will be promoted to a common second round where all panel members will participate in the same survey.

The Key Concepts will be presented to panelists as they are presented on the IHC website (www.informedhealthchoices.org). The text on this website has been developed for non-researchers, and we have sought feedback on how understandable and clear the text earlier. However, the text has not been rewritten with TCIM specifically in mind. We recognize that this may pose a challenge for some panelists and will be open to questions related to clarity.

3. Consensus meeting: In this stage we will hold an online workshop to confirm the list of relevant IHC key concepts to be included in Your Life Your Health for TCIM, and open for feedback regarding terminology for each prioritized criterion.

Sampling and recruitment

We will aim to include a diverse set of panelists to represent diverse academic disciplines (e.g., education, health, social work), experience, roles (academics, decision makers, other stakeholders), familiarity with IHC key concepts, systematic reviews and qualitative research. We will invite approximately 230 people with the aim of including 80 panelists in Round 1. See Appendix 1 for invitation text and fields to be included in online participation form.

We will use purposive and convenience sampling via the research team's professional networks. We will invite some authors of relevant papers identified in the scoping review and use a snowballing technique requesting identified experts to suggest other experts, practitioner, patient and/or user organizations (snowballing technique). We will aim for diversity among participants by considering the following factors:

- Geographic representation (e.g., across WHO regions)
- Professional roles (such as patient representatives, experts in consumer communication, researchers, clinicians, and policymakers)
- Gender balance
- Varied experience and backgrounds

We expect attrition during rounds one to three to be approximately 40%. We will then aim to have a final sample of at least 50 panelists.

We will send invitations to potential panelists informing them of the scope and objectives of the project. Those who agree to participate will fill out confidentiality, consent and conflict of interest forms. Panelists will be offered the opportunity to be acknowledged or a role as co-author on any eventual papers when contributions warrant so.

We will invite key stakeholders by email, provided with a link to a Nettskjema form where they will be asked to provide the following details:

- name
- role
- institution/organization
- country
- email address
- explicitly confirm informed consent
- fill out a conflict of interest statement (according to guidelines from WHO)

Introductory Seminar

We will invite panel members to a digital introductory seminar. During this seminar we will present panel members with a short description of the activities and research up until this point. We will outline the criteria that will be sent out in the eDelphi. We will also present an overview of the eDelphi process and final consensus meeting along with corresponding dates. This seminar will be recorded and shared with panel members who are unable to attend.

Online Delphi (eDelphi) procedure

We will conduct three rounds of the eDelphi survey. Following recruitment of panel members (see sampling and sample above), we will conduct the Delphi study online using an online format (either Delphi software if available or Nettskjema, an online data collection form). For each round, panelists will be sent a link to the survey in an email with details related to due date and expectations. Panelists will be given 1-2 weeks to complete each round.

Each round will take approximately 1-2 weeks (total 4-6 weeks). Three rounds are considered ideal to avoid respondent fatigue while still ensuring maximum opportunity to achieve consensus among respondents (France et al. 2015; Okoli & Pawlowski 2004). We will send reminders via email three days before the due date to all panelists.

Below is a description of each round:

Round 1 (exploring): Present existing IHC concepts together with concepts identified in the scoping review that may be particularly relevant for assessing reliability of TCIM claims. Participants will score the relevance of each concept using five-point Likert scale (Extremely relevant, very relevant, moderately relevant, slightly relevant, not at all relevant) as well as an option for “uncertain”. Participants will also be asked to identify any missing concepts relevant to assessing the reliability of a claim about a TCIM (open text, maximum 40 word limit). Key concepts with 70% or more consensus will be promoted to Round 2. We have set 70% as this is not only standard practice, but complete unanimity is both unachievable and arguably not necessarily a good thing whereby mixed outcomes are a “record and reminder that there are alternative points of view to the one that prevailed at the time of the vote” (Beaty & Moore 2010; Diamond 2014).

Round 2 (prioritizing): We will present a summarized list of all items from Round 1 with group responses prior to beginning this round. We will present a list of items with moderate or strong consensus promoted from Round 1 back to panelists (concepts are promoted if there is 70% or higher consensus that they are relevant or very relevant; 70-80% is considered moderate consensus, and $\geq 80\%$ is considered strong consensus). All panelists in this round will receive the same list.

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Participants to score relevance of each concept using five-point Likert scale (Extremely relevant, very relevant, moderately relevant, slightly relevant, not at all relevant) as well as an option for “uncertain”.

Round 3 (achieving consensus): Concepts are promoted to this stage if they achieved 70% or higher consensus. We will present a summarized list of items from Round 2 with group responses prior to beginning this round. We will ask participants to fill out judgement criteria for each of the promoted concepts (see Table 1 adapted from Li et al. (2024)). Concepts with 70% or higher consensus on the judgment criteria (e.g., “Yes”, see Table 1, column 6) will be promoted to the consensus meeting.

Participants will be given the opportunity to suggest different wording for each Key Concept that is considered more relevant for TCIM under the heading “other comments”. This feedback will not be used in the consensus meeting, but may inform the development of health messages in this next stage of the larger project to develop digital resources for the WHO website.

Consensus meeting: Following the final round of the eDelphi process, panelists who have participated in two or more rounds will be asked to comment on the list of prioritized concepts in plenum delivered digitally via webinar. The goal of this meeting will be to establish a list of relevant Key Concepts to inform WP2. Wording of the concepts may be discussed during this seminar, but it is the focus of the next stage of the project to develop health messages for the prioritized concepts and therefore coming up with the final wording of the relevant concepts is outside the scope of this Delphi survey.

Table 1. Judgement criteria used in Round 3 (adapted from Li et al. (2024))

Key Concept	Criteria				Judgement	Comments	
	How easy is it to understand this concept?	How relevant (i.e., of current significance or importance) do you think this concept is?	How likely is it that people are already aware of this concept?	How helpful do you think this concept is in supporting people to assess treatment claims or make well-informed choices?	Do you think this concept should be included in information materials for people making decisions about TCIM?	If uncertain or No, please state why:	Other comment:

Data analysis

Data will be collated after each round and fed back to panel members at the subsequent round (descriptive statistics for the data including frequency and percentage of responses) illustrating the level of consensus for each criterion. This will be sent to panel members before each subsequent round where they will apply judgement criteria.

Qualitative data (from open-ended question about additional concepts) will be analysed using inductive categorical analysis (we will categorize responses into groups that emerge from the data (Mayring 2000)). We will first determine whether free-text responses can be placed into an existing A Delphi survey to identify Informed Health Choices Key Concepts relevant for decision making related to traditional, complementary and integrative medicine: Protocol

Key Concept. For remaining suggested additional concepts, we will, to the extent possible, ensure that emerging categories are internally consistent (data within the category fit together), externally distinct (categories are meaningfully different from each other), and clearly defined (researchers provide descriptions and inclusion/exclusion criteria)

Following Round 3 we will prepare descriptive statistics for the data and present this prior to the consensus meeting. Key concepts that have a judgement of “Yes” among 70% or more of participants during this round will be promoted for consideration during the final consensus meeting.

The consensus meeting will not be recorded but detailed minutes (without names associated with quotes) will be taken by one member while one member facilitates.

We will explicitly report dissenting opinions from each round at the subsequent round. A dissenting opinion will be defined as an opinion where between 10-20% of participants indicated the opposite viewpoint for a concept where there was consensus rate of 70% or higher (e.g., 10-20% of panelists indicated a concept was “not at all relevant” when 70% indicated that it was “relevant” or “very relevant” or when 70% indicated “Not at all relevant” and 10-20% indicated “Very Relevant” or “Relevant”). When reporting dissenting opinions in the subsequent round, all panelists will be given the opportunity revise their rating or retain their original rating and provide reasoning for their position using free-text response (maximum 40 words). We will conduct short-form thematic analysis to identify majority reasoning themes, minority or dissenting reasoning themes and assumptions underlying each position.

Patient and public engagement

The nature of a Delphi consensus survey is to seek input from a wide variety of interest holders. In this way, patient and public engagement is central to the study. We have also received and incorporated feedback on the protocol from three people with backgrounds related to TCIM.

Ethical considerations

It was not necessary to subject this study to ethical review as it is not considered health research under Norwegian law. However, we will adhere to ethical principles in the design and conduct of the survey, including ensuring anonymity during each Delphi round, and informing panelists of the objective of the study. We also aim to respect diversity of opinion and will ensure interactions are welcoming and respectful. All participants will provide informed consent implicitly by clicking on the link to the survey. Participants will be asked to fill out a conflict of interest statement before participating in the final consensus webinar.

Data management

Data will be collected via an online form. Participants will be provided with an identification number in their email invitation and be asked to use that when participating in each round of the Delphi.

HMK (FHI) will collect participant details, and once a participant has agreed to participate, HMK will send out invitations from her email to an online introductory webinar, and three rounds of a Delphi survey. Finally, participants who have participated in at least two rounds of the Delphi survey will be invited to an online consensus webinar.

The findings from each stage of the Delphi will be collected anonymously via nettskjema. HMK will collate the responses, save the data in a research folder and share the anonymous data with the research group for analyse before embarking on the next round of the Delphi.

HMK will take notes during the consensus webinar, but it will not be recorded.

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Panelists who have participated in the Delphi and consensus webinar will be offered the opportunity to comment on the final report. Panelists who comment on the final manuscript, will be offered the opportunity to be included as a co-author as part of the “Reasoned advisory group” with their names published in the acknowledgements section (or similar) of the final report or publication.

Reflexivity

The principal investigator (HMK) leads the Informed Health Choices network. Co-investigator LSW is Director of the Cochrane Complementary Medicine Field. Co-investigator JH is an academic general practitioner with a clinical interest in TCIM and Director of an independent consultancy company, Health Research Group Pty. Limited.

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References

- Agu JC, Hee-Jeon Y, Steel A, Adams J. A Systematic Review of Traditional, Complementary and Alternative Medicine Use Amongst Ethnic Minority Populations: A Focus Upon Prevalence, Drivers, Integrative Use, Health Outcomes, Referrals and Use of Information Sources. *J Immigr Minor Health*. 2019 Oct;21(5):1137-1156. doi: 10.1007/s10903-018-0832-4. PMID: 30382488.
- Barnes LAJ, Barclay L, McCaffery K, Aslani P. Complementary medicine products used in pregnancy and lactation and an examination of the information sources accessed pertaining to maternal health literacy: a systematic review of qualitative studies. *BMC Complement Altern Med*. 2018 Jul 31;18(1):229. doi: 10.1186/s12906-018-2283-9. PMID: 30064415; PMCID: PMC6069845.
- Beatty, J., & Moore, A. (2010). Should we aim for consensus? *Episteme*, 7(3), 198–214.
- Dahlgren A, Semakula D, Chesire F, Mugisha M, Nakyejwe E, Nsangi A, et al. Critical thinking about treatment effects in Eastern Africa: development and Rasch analysis of an assessment tool [version 1; peer review: awaiting peer review] *F1000Research*. 2023;12(887):<https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.132052.1>.
- Diamond IR, Grant RC, Feldman BM, Pencharz PB, Ling SC, Moore AM, Wales PW. Defining consensus: a systematic review recommends methodologic criteria for reporting of Delphi studies. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2014 Apr;67(4):401-9. doi: 10.1016/j.jclinepi.2013.12.002. PMID: 24581294.
- France E, Ring N, Noyes J, Maxwell M, Jepson R, Duncan E, et al. Protocol-developing meta-ethnography reporting guidelines (eMERGe). *BMC Medical Research Methodology*. 2015;15(1):1-14 Harnett JE, Leach MJ, Karzon R, McIntyre E. Mental Health Literacy and Education of Complementary Medicine Practitioners: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Adm Policy Ment Health*. 2024;51(2):217-25.

- Hohmann E, Cote MP, Brand JC. Research Pearls: Expert Consensus Based Evidence Using the Delphi Method. *Arthroscopy*. 2018 Dec;34(12):3278-3282. doi: 10.1016/j.arthro.2018.10.004. PMID: 30509437.
- Jünger S, Payne SA, Brine J, Radbruch L, Brearley SG. Guidance on Conducting and REporting DElphi Studies (CREDES) in palliative care: Recommendations based on a methodological systematic review. *Palliative medicine*. 2017;31(8):684-706.
- Li, M., Devane, D., Beecher, C., Dowling, M., Duffy, A. G., Duggan, C., ... & Tierney, M. (2024). Prioritising Key Concepts for informed health choices in cancer: An evidence-based online educational programme. *PEC innovation*, 5, 100311.
- Mayring, P. Qualitative Content Analysis. *Forum: Qualitative Social Research*. 2000 Vol 1(2) Art 20.
- McIntyre E, Harnett J, Adams J, Steel A. The role of complementary medicine health literacy in health communication and decision-making, *European Journal of Public Health*, Volume 30, Issue Supplement_5, September 2020, ckaa166.031, <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/ckaa166.031>
- Muscat D, Hinton R, Nutbeam D, Kenney E, Kuruvilla S, Jakab Z. Universal health information is essential for universal health coverage. *Fam Med Community Health*. 2023 May;11(2):e002090. doi: 10.1136/fmch-2022-002090. PMID: 37225258; PMCID: PMC10231010.
- Okoli C, Pawlowski SD. The Delphi method as a research tool: an example, design considerations and applications. *Information & management*. 2004;42(1):15-29 Oxman AD, García LM. Comparison of the Informed Health Choices Key Concepts Framework to other frameworks relevant to teaching and learning how to think critically about health claims and choices: a systematic review. *F1000Research*. 2020;9:164.
- Qian Z, Wang GY, Henning M, Chen Y. Understanding health literacy from a traditional Chinese medicine perspective. *J Integr Med*. 2023 May;21(3):215-220. doi: 10.1016/j.joim.2023.03.001. Epub 2023 Mar 4. PMID: 36935313.
- Tangkiatkumjai M, Boardman H, Walker DM. Potential factors that influence usage of complementary and alternative medicine worldwide: a systematic review. *BMC Complement Med Ther*. 2020 Nov 23;20(1):363. doi: 10.1186/s12906-020-03157-2. PMID: 33228697; PMCID: PMC7686746.
- Turoff M, Linstone HA (eds.). *The Delphi method-techniques and applications*. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley Publishing Company. 2002.
- Wieland LS, Hunter J, Dorris CS. Concepts underlying choices about TCIM: protocol for a rapid scoping review of the literature. In: *Open Science Framework* [<https://osf.io/v9yk6>], Washington DC: Center for Open Science. (date created/modified August 3, 2025)(accessed October 4, 2025).
- World Health Organization (WHO). Division of Health Promotion E, Communication. *Health promotion glossary* Geneva: World Health Organization; [updated 1998]. Available from: <https://iris.who.int/handle/10665/64546>. [Accessed 10 March 2022.]
- Zhang M, Cai A, Jin K, Huang J, Li D, He M, Gao R. Scientific epistemology beliefs and acceptance of Traditional Chinese Medicine: A multigroup analysis based on the UTAUT model in Southern China. *Heliyon*. 2024 Jun 17;10(12):e33136. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e33136. PMID: 39022003; PMCID: PMC11252763.

